

The Bootstrap Mean Filter for Image Restoration

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Abstract

A bootstrap mean is calculated as follows. An artificial data set is generated by randomly sampling the original data set. A trimmed mean is then calculated for each of the artificial data set. These steps are repeated many times to produce a set of trimmed means. The bootstrap mean is the average of these trimmed means. The bootstrap mean is a more robust estimate of the true mean and the estimation of error is the usual standard deviation. Recent advances in fast computers make it feasible to calculate the bootstrap mean.

A bootstrap mean filter was developed and tested using synthetic data with random noise added. Comparisons to mean, median, and trimmed-mean filters show that the bootstrap mean filter is superior in the removal of random noise and the retention of edge information. Implementation in special purpose hardware of this filter is desirable because of its heavy computational requirement. Some candidate solutions are suggested.

Introduction

Image data collected by a sensor suffers from quality degradation. A good quality image should display shape edges at physical surface boundaries, and show smooth gradual intensity change on the physical surfaces. Such an image would allow edge information to be extracted unambiguously by the human eye or by an automated system.

The most common kind of image degradation is the additive noise represented by the following equation.

$$x(i, j) = x_o(i, j) + n(i, j)$$

where

$x(i, j)$ is the intensity at pixel location (i,j),

$x_o(i, j)$ is the noiseless (ideal) pixel at (i,j),

$n(i, j)$ is the random noise.

A noise reduction filter will attempt to estimate $x_o(i, j)$ given $x(i, j)$. The better the filter, the closer to the ideal noiseless value its estimates are. Such noise reduction filters are usually some form of low-pass filter that smooth out noisy spikes in the data. However, they also

lose some of the subtle edge information. Therefore, the trade-off is usually between smoothing and edge preservation. This paper discusses the results of the bootstrap mean filter that reproduces the noiseless pixels more closely and yet preserves more of the edge information. The bootstrap statistical method was discussed in Efron and Tibshirani [1].

Test Data

A checkerboard of 100 by 100 pixels with 10 squares by 10 squares was used to test the filter performance. (Each square has 10 by 10 pixels.) Before noise was introduced, the adjacent squares contained values alternating between 1.0 and -1.0. Noises of various amplitudes and statistical characteristics were introduced by adding to the nominal values (1.0 and -1.0). Random noise levels of 0.1 to 1.0 (standard deviation) were introduced using Gaussian, uniform, and Poisson statistical distribution.

Comparisons of the performance of the filters were also conducted using computer generated images of an airplane. This image has a black background (pixel value = 0) and a maximum brightness of 255.

Filter Performance Metrics

Using the checkerboard data, knowing what the perfect image should look like, the following measures were used to gauge the performance of the filters. For measuring the restoration of the degraded image, the root-mean-square of the difference between the noisy image and the ideal checkerboard were calculated and compared as follows:

$$RMS = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{row} \sum_{j=1}^{col} (x(i, j) - x_o(i, j))^2}{(row * col - 1)}}$$

where

$x(i, j)$ is the pixel at the (i, j) position in the noisy checkerboard.

$x_o(i, j)$ is the pixel at the (i, j) position in the noiseless checkerboard.

A smaller value here indicates that the filter does a better job in restoring the noisy pixels to match the ideal

checkerboard.

An often contradicting measure of filter performance is edge preservation. Most restoration is performed by applying a smoothing filter, which tends to wash out the edge information that is important in computer vision applications. Since the location and size of the edges are well-defined in a checkerboard, a measure of how well the filter preserves edges is as follows:

$$\text{edge strength} = \frac{\sum_{i,j} |x_{ij} - x_{i+1j+1}|}{n}$$

where

- x_{ij} are the pixel value at location (i,j),
- i and j are multiples of 10,
- n is the number of pairs of edge pixels.

Procedure

The bootstrap mean of the pixels within a small moving window (3x3 and 5x5) was calculated by using a 20% trimmed mean and 200 artificially generated random data samples. A standard deviation was also calculated for each pixel location at the center of the moving window. Intermediate results of two arrays were obtained, one for the bootstrap mean and another for the standard deviation. The standard deviation array was then used as a conditional filter to give the final filtered image in the following fashion.

The average (μ_{sd}) and standard deviation (σ_{sd}) of the standard deviation over the entire image (less the boundary pixels) were then calculated and used to determine whether the bootstrap mean or the original pixel value should be used in the final filtered image. If the standard deviation was greater than ($\mu_{sd} + \sigma_{sd}$) then the original pixel value was used instead of the bootstrap mean. The rationale was

that the larger than normal standard deviation was likely to be found near the edges. Results of experimentation with ($\mu_{sd} + 3\sigma_{sd}$) as a condition were also obtained.

Similar conditional filtering was also added to the basic median, mean, and trimmed mean filter to allow a better comparison with the above bootstrap mean filter. However, only the condition ($\mu_{sd} + \sigma_{sd}$) was used because $3\sigma_{sd}$ is usually quite large for these other filters.

Results

1. Checkerboard

The mean, median, trimmed mean, and bootstrap mean filters were used to filter the noisy checkerboard images. Tables 1 and 2 below show the resulting performance metrics of these filters on images with additive Gaussian noise. These tables display the root-mean-squares residual (RMS diff.) and the edge strength as a function of the noise level (standard deviation) and filter type. Results for additive noise with uniform and Poisson statistical distributions are comparable.

The bootstrap mean filter proved superior in retaining edges. While the other filters lost more edge strength as the size of the moving window was increased from 3x3 to 5x5, the bootstrap mean filter actually improved in edge strength. The bootstrap mean filter retained more edge strength while more closely matching the original noiseless checkerboard. The other filters apparently outperformed the bootstrap in image restoration under very noisy condition (sd = 1). This is probably due to the fact that very noisy pixels at the edges were put back into the filtered image by the bootstrap mean filter more often than by the other filters.

noise level	original noisy		median filter		trimmed mean filter	
stand. dev.	RMS diff.	edge str	RMS diff.	edge str	RMS diff.	edge str
0.1	0.08	2.005	0.054	2.001	0.044	2.001
0.5	0.4	2.028	0.276	1.9	0.245	1.898
0.707	0.567	2.024	0.398	1.72	0.355	1.728
1	0.799	2.151	0.556	1.462	0.489	1.479
noise level	mean filter		bootstrap		bootstrap 3 sigma	
stand. dev.	RMS diff.	edge str	RMS diff.	edge str	RMS diff.	edge str
0.1	0.044	2.001	0.045	2.001	0.046	2
0.5	0.235	1.875	0.244	1.973	0.236	1.928
0.707	0.342	1.701	0.374	1.91	0.357	1.81
1	0.476	1.465	0.569	1.763	0.527	1.679

Table 1. Filter performance results using a 3x3 moving window

noise level	original noisy		median filter		trimmed mean filter	
stand. dev.	RMS diff.	edge str	RMS diff.	edge str	RMS diff.	edge str
0.1	0.08	2.005	0.049	2.001	0.043	2.001
0.5	0.4	2.028	0.266	1.905	0.27	1.886
0.707	0.565	2.023	0.381	1.708	0.384	1.694
1	0.799	2.151	0.509	1.402	0.505	1.404
noise level	mean filter		bootstrap		bootstrap 3 sigma	
stand. dev.	RMS diff.	edge str	RMS diff.	edge str	RMS diff.	edge str
0.1	0.118	2.001	0.059	2.001	0.063	2.001
0.5	0.292	1.881	0.253	1.999	0.247	1.996
0.707	0.392	1.688	0.367	1.977	0.357	1.928
1	0.505	1.399	0.552	1.865	0.525	1.784

Table 2. Filter performance results using a 5x5 moving window

Figure 1 below illustrates an example of the input and filtered images. Comparing to the median filter, the

bootstrap mean filter produced a smoother image with sharper and more distinct edge boundaries.

Figure 1. Results of the median filter and bootstrap mean filters. The noisy image was created by adding Gaussian noise (standard deviation = 0.707) to the ideal checkerboard.

2. Airplane

A straight median filter (without the conditional filtering) was used to compare to the bootstrap mean filter. The mean and standard deviation of the intensity in the original noiseless image (row x column = 329x150) are 38.74 and 33.00 respectively. A noisy image was created

by adding Gaussian noise. Table 2 shows the results after applying a median filter and a bootstrap mean filter with 200 artificial samples. The bootstrap mean filter is only marginally better than the median filter. It is possible that this particular image contains too few edges which the bootstrap mean filter is designed to handle.

	original data	noise level	median 3x3	bootstrap 3x3
standard dev.	33.0	23.34	11.68	10.87
s/n (dB)		3	9	9.6

Table 2. Results of median and bootstrap mean filters on the image of an airplane.

Discussions

The bootstrap mean filter implemented here performed well comparing to other common noise reduction filters. Its advantages are that (1) the mean estimate is more robust, (2) the standard deviation used is a good estimate of the error in the mean calculated and hence more useful in determining the reliability of the filtered pixel, (3) the method is independent of the statistical characteristics of the noise. This bootstrap approach can be extended to calculating the standard deviation of the median, maximum, or minimum within a small moving window.

The major drawback to this approach is that it requires a tremendous amount of computing time. For a 100x100 image, it typically requires 30 minutes of CPU time on a Silicon Graphics Indigo(TM) workstation. Hardware implementation of the bootstrap is almost imperative. The following schematic (figure 2) shows a possible hardware implementation of a bootstrap for the the median filter. The median filter could use an analog VLSI hardware such as that developed by Kontogiorgia and Andreou [2]. A bootstrap minimum or maximum filter is similar and could utilize a hardware implementation of a winner-take-all neural net in place of the median filter.

Figure 2. A schematic of a hardware implementation of the bootstrap for the median filter. The 9 pixels from a 3x3 moving window and 9 random bits (with 8 zeros and 1 one at a random position) is input into a set of 9 AND gates. The set of 9 random bits used in each group of 9 AND gates is generated separately.

References

1. Efron, B. and Tibshirani, R., 1991, Statistical analysis in the computer age, *Science*, Vol. 253, p. 390-395.
2. Kontogiorgia, S.A. and Andreou, A.G., 1989, A spatial mean and median filter in analog VLSI, in *Proceedings of Information Sciences and Systems*, Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, MD.

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